

DIVINFOOD

Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based food

Deliverable D1.4

Typology of short and mid-tier chains valuing biodiversity, including SMART indexes of agrobiodiversity use in marketing and data

Additional material to Appendix 2

Due date of deliverable: M24

Actual submission date: M29

Start date of the project: March 1st, 2022

Duration: 60 months

Organisation name of lead contractor: Agri Kulti Nonprofit Ltd.

Revision: V4

Dissemination level	
Public – PU	X
Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including Commission Services) – CO	
Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC – CI	

Sources: Terre Inovia, Terre Univia, Agreste, FAOSTAT

Year	NUC	Variety
2022	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2021	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2020	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2019	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2018	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2017	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2016	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2015	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2014	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2013	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2012	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2011	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2010	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2009	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2008	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2007	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2006	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2005	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2004	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2003	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2002	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2001	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
2000	<i>Cicerarietium</i> - Chickpea	All
<hr/>		
2022	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2021	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2020	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2019	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2018	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2017	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2016	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2015	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2014	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)

2013 <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2012 <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2011 <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2010 <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2009 <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2008 <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2007 <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2006 <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2005 <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2004 <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2003 <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2002 <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2001 <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2000 <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> - Common bean	All (certainly including the NUCs studied)
2022 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2021 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2020 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2019 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2018 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2017 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2016 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2015 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2014 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2013 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2012 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2011 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2010 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2009 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2008 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2007 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2006 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2005 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2004 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2003 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2002 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2001 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All

2000 <i>Lens culinaris</i> - Lentils	All
2022 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2021 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2020 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2019 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2018 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2017 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2016 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2015 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2014 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2013 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2012 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2011 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2010 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2009 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2008 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2007 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2006 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2005 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2004 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2003 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2002 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2001 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2000 Lupine	All (including <i>Lupinus angustifolius</i> and <i>Lupinus alnus</i>)
2022 <i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2021 <i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2020 <i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All

2019	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2018	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2017	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2016	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2015	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2014	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2013	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2012	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2011	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2010	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2009	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2008	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2007	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2006	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2005	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2004	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2003	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2002	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2001	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All
2000	<i>Vicia faba</i> - Faba bean	All

2022	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2021	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2020	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2019	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2018	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2017	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2016	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2015	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2014	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2013	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2012	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2011	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2010	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2009	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2008	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2007	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2006	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2005	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2004	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2003	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2002	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2001	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All
2000	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> - Cowpea	All

2022	<i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2021	<i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2020	<i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2018	<i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2017	<i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2016	<i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc

2015 <i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2014 <i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2013 <i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2012 <i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2011 <i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2010 <i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2009 <i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2008 <i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2007 <i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2006 <i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2005 <i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2004 <i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2003 <i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2002 <i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2001 <i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc
2000 <i>Pisum sativum</i> - Pea	All (certainly including the NUCs stuc

Production (tonnes)	Import (million EUR) where available	Sales to processors or intermediaries (tonnes) where available	Sales directly to consumers (tonnes) where available	Sales within agricultural enterprises (tonnes) where available
	22322	17,04325912	n/a	n/a
	25442	7,518133884	n/a	n/a
	39137	7,088975296	n/a	n/a
n/a		6,706718138	n/a	n/a
n/a		11,8158658	n/a	n/a
n/a		13,76229003	n/a	n/a
n/a		9,025886717	n/a	n/a
n/a		4,474933427	n/a	n/a
n/a		5,076376512	n/a	n/a
n/a		5,567352672	n/a	n/a
n/a		5,827862487	n/a	n/a
n/a		6,140416445	n/a	n/a
n/a		4,547635746	n/a	n/a
n/a		4,827989414	n/a	n/a
n/a		5,21222142	n/a	n/a
n/a		7,045537413	n/a	n/a
n/a		6,338066766	n/a	n/a
n/a		5,38117104	n/a	n/a
n/a		5,01098103	n/a	n/a
n/a		5,245322267	n/a	n/a
n/a		6,747203083	n/a	n/a
n/a		9,46977974	n/a	n/a
n/a		8,633278228	n/a	n/a
<hr/>				
n/a		52,72731544	n/a	n/a
n/a		53,99156473	n/a	n/a
n/a		58,37526453	n/a	n/a
n/a		51,9609866	n/a	n/a
n/a		44,85693526	n/a	n/a
	11047,00	47,43373715	n/a	n/a
	7785,00	46,30467925	n/a	n/a
	9286,00	59,99458399	n/a	n/a
	8022,00	62,59884515	n/a	n/a

7542,00			
	52,62172572	n/a	n/a
7395,00			
	49,88472838	n/a	n/a
6884,80			
	45,72006185	n/a	n/a
7521,00			
	40,21067396	n/a	n/a
4892,30			
	38,22944115	n/a	n/a
6142,00			
	44,52950606	n/a	n/a
6690,70			
	38,86918436	n/a	n/a
8055,00			
	33,85536833	n/a	n/a
8974,00			
	34,0062348	n/a	n/a
7648,00			
	33,3582183	n/a	n/a
9224,30			
	39,71825359	n/a	n/a
8693,00			
	44,12883327	n/a	n/a
8901,40			
	43,11130078	n/a	n/a
8860,00			
	43,14034152	n/a	n/a
29245	44,5770184	n/a	n/a
20019	29,30398136	n/a	n/a
29406	23,8006414	n/a	n/a
n/a	19,50826018	n/a	n/a
n/a	28,95115748	n/a	n/a
39994,00	31,84615336	n/a	n/a
23901,00	28,06938669	n/a	n/a
22161,00	26,68910526	n/a	n/a
22033,00	19,64523792	n/a	n/a
22793,00	20,94385053	n/a	n/a
25195,20	19,43009976	n/a	n/a
23343,60	21,00157663	n/a	n/a
19545,00	21,41307484	n/a	n/a
13034,80	16,76659154	n/a	n/a
7957,00	19,74636602	n/a	n/a
9825,30	11,73038506	n/a	n/a
14019,00	11,13047746	n/a	n/a
15542,00	12,0778824	n/a	n/a
8054,00	9,552434265	n/a	n/a
9026,00	11,89589472	n/a	n/a
8018,00	12,41379112	n/a	n/a
6279,00	13,0301666	n/a	n/a

11874,00	14,93620087	n/a	n/a	n/a
11020,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
15130,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
13030,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
7110,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
6960,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
12547,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
16804,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
17357,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
15020,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
7622,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
6197,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
7322,80				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
16205,50				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
8326,50				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
6819,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
11340,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
16562,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
17597,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
21966,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
23957,60				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
35272,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
34481,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
33565,00				
n/a		n/a	n/a	n/a
157853,00	27,23231906	n/a	n/a	n/a
184198,00	15,89613531	n/a	n/a	n/a
148407,00	8,642123645	n/a	n/a	n/a

672908,70	8,82273294 n/a	n/a	n/a
538587,00	7,984269694 n/a	n/a	n/a
498723,00	8,491116616 n/a	n/a	n/a
561521,70	8,599366002 n/a	n/a	n/a
670079,00	5,768509779 n/a	n/a	n/a
1073331,00	7,646340229 n/a	n/a	n/a
546800,00	9,256465763 n/a	n/a	n/a
450618,10	10,71662762 n/a	n/a	n/a
594095,00	10,2464603 n/a	n/a	n/a
1016190,00	5,099309911 n/a	n/a	n/a
1331286,00	3,55099392 n/a	n/a	n/a
1680782,00	5,105208735 n/a	n/a	n/a
1616661,00	6,02857647 n/a	n/a	n/a
1662611,00	8,359093962 n/a	n/a	n/a
1660000,00	10,66886797 n/a	n/a	n/a
1936500,00	11,68759617 n/a	n/a	n/a

n/a n/a

Source of official data: KSH - Central Statistical Office, Hungary

Year	NUC	Production (tonnes)	Import (million HUF) where available	Sales to processors or intermediaries (tonnes) where available
	Common Bean			
2015	(Phaseolus vulgaris)	1467	5168	786
	Common Bean			
2016	(Phaseolus vulgaris)	1600	6656	1239
	Common Bean			
2017	(Phaseolus vulgaris)	1713	5319	1015
	Common Bean			
2018	(Phaseolus vulgaris)	1647	7255	855
	Common Bean			
2019	(Phaseolus vulgaris)	1415	7089	1108
	Common Bean			
2020	(Phaseolus vulgaris)	1157	8665	646
	Common Bean			
2021	(Phaseolus vulgaris)	778	8153	355
	Common Bean			
2022	(Phaseolus vulgaris)	234	11476	160
2009	Lentils (Lens culinaris)	24	n/a	n/a
2010	Lentils (Lens culinaris)	57	n/a	n/a
2011	Lentils (Lens culinaris)	41	n/a	n/a
2012	Lentils (Lens culinaris)	20	n/a	n/a
2013	Lentils (Lens culinaris)	2	n/a	n/a
2014	Lentils (Lens culinaris)	1	n/a	n/a
2015	Lentils (Lens culinaris)	8	n/a	n/a
2016	Lentils (Lens culinaris)	19	n/a	n/a
2017	Lentils (Lens culinaris)	20	n/a	n/a
2018	Lentils (Lens culinaris)	13	n/a	n/a
2019	Lentils (Lens culinaris)	3	n/a	n/a
2020	Lentils (Lens culinaris)	340	n/a	n/a

2021 Lentils (<i>Lens culinaris</i>)	238	n/a	n/a
2022 Lentils (<i>Lens culinaris</i>)	217	n/a	n/a
2023 Lentils (<i>Lens culinaris</i>)	n/a	n/a	n/a
<hr/>			
2009 Chickpeas	10	n/a	n/a
2010 Chickpeas	4	n/a	n/a
2011 Chickpeas	6	n/a	n/a
2012 Chickpeas	9	n/a	n/a
2013 Chickpeas	36	n/a	n/a
2014 Chickpeas	90	n/a	n/a
2015 Chickpeas	70	n/a	n/a
2016 Chickpeas	126	n/a	n/a
2017 Chickpeas	134	n/a	n/a
2018 Chickpeas	378	n/a	n/a
2019 Chickpeas	686	n/a	n/a
2020 Chickpeas	210	n/a	n/a
2021 Chickpeas	159	n/a	n/a
2022 Chickpeas	143	n/a	n/a
2023 Chickpeas	n/a	n/a	n/a
<hr/>			
Pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>) -			
2013 green	67646	n/a	n/a
Pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>) -			
2014 green	87646	n/a	n/a
Pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>) -			
2015 green	94545	19	62533
Pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>) -			
2016 green	111231	72	50616
Pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>) -			
2017 green	128306	29	52481
Pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>) -			
2018 green	89809	26	35532
Pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>) -			
2019 green	91480	67	34287
Pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>) -			
2020 green	90017	101	41792
Pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>) -			
2021 green	86786	131	43302
Pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>) -			
2022 green	82336	560	42007
Pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>) -			
2023 green	n/a	n/a	n/a
<hr/>			
Pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>) -			
2015 dry	63644	1437	6812
Pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>) -			
2016 dry	47083	868	6175
Pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>) -			
2017 dry	47626	1081	2223

Pea (Pisum sativum) -			
2018 dry	31404	1317	4861
Pea (Pisum sativum) -			
2019 dry	37979	1235	5199
Pea (Pisum sativum) -			
2020 dry	24301	1735	5089
Pea (Pisum sativum) -			
2021 dry	30233	1992	4942
Pea (Pisum sativum) -			
2022 dry	24356	5221	4835
<hr/>			
2009 Lupines	556 n/a	n/a	
2010 Lupines	25 n/a	n/a	
2011 Lupines	41 n/a	n/a	
2012 Lupines	32 n/a	n/a	
2013 Lupines	75 n/a	n/a	
2014 Lupines	194 n/a	n/a	
2015 Lupines	136 n/a	n/a	
2016 Lupines	449 n/a	n/a	
2017 Lupines	395 n/a	n/a	
2018 Lupines	261 n/a	n/a	
2019 Lupines	317 n/a	n/a	
2020 Lupines	200 n/a	n/a	
2021 Lupines	203 n/a	n/a	
2022 Lupines	132 n/a	n/a	
<hr/>			
2009 Faba bean - Vicia faba	125 n/a	n/a	
2010 Faba bean - Vicia faba	196 n/a	n/a	
2011 Faba bean - Vicia faba	206 n/a	n/a	
2012 Faba bean - Vicia faba	163 n/a	n/a	
2013 Faba bean - Vicia faba	205 n/a	n/a	
2014 Faba bean - Vicia faba	261 n/a	n/a	
2015 Faba bean - Vicia faba	166 n/a	n/a	
2016 Faba bean - Vicia faba	335 n/a	n/a	
2017 Faba bean - Vicia faba	110 n/a	n/a	
2018 Faba bean - Vicia faba	162 n/a	n/a	
2019 Faba bean - Vicia faba	127 n/a	n/a	
2020 Faba bean - Vicia faba	114 n/a	n/a	
2021 Faba bean - Vicia faba	98 n/a	n/a	

2022	Faba bean - <i>Vicia faba</i>		41	n/a	n/a
	Cowpea - <i>Vigna</i>				
2009	unguiculata		7	n/a	n/a
	Cowpea - <i>Vigna</i>				
2010	unguiculata	n/a		n/a	n/a
	Cowpea - <i>Vigna</i>				
2011	unguiculata	n/a		n/a	n/a
	Cowpea - <i>Vigna</i>				
2012	unguiculata	n/a		n/a	n/a
	Cowpea - <i>Vigna</i>				
2013	unguiculata	n/a		n/a	n/a
	Cowpea - <i>Vigna</i>				
2014	unguiculata	n/a		n/a	n/a
	Cowpea - <i>Vigna</i>				
2015	unguiculata		24	n/a	n/a
	Cowpea - <i>Vigna</i>				
2016	unguiculata		7	n/a	n/a
	Cowpea - <i>Vigna</i>				
2017	unguiculata		5	n/a	n/a
	Cowpea - <i>Vigna</i>				
2018	unguiculata		25	n/a	n/a
	Cowpea - <i>Vigna</i>				
2019	unguiculata		47	n/a	n/a
	Cowpea - <i>Vigna</i>				
2020	unguiculata		127	n/a	n/a
	Cowpea - <i>Vigna</i>				
2021	unguiculata		6	n/a	n/a
	Cowpea - <i>Vigna</i>				
2022	unguiculata		5	n/a	n/a
	Cowpea - <i>Vigna</i>				
2023	unguiculata	n/a		n/a	n/a
	Grass pea (<i>Lathyrus</i>				
2009	sativus)		25	n/a	n/a
	Grass pea (<i>Lathyrus</i>				
2010	sativus)		63	n/a	n/a
	Grass pea (<i>Lathyrus</i>				
2011	sativus)	n/a		n/a	n/a
	Grass pea (<i>Lathyrus</i>				
2012	sativus)		4	n/a	n/a
	Grass pea (<i>Lathyrus</i>				
2013	sativus)		6	n/a	n/a
	Grass pea (<i>Lathyrus</i>				
2014	sativus)		4	n/a	n/a
	Grass pea (<i>Lathyrus</i>				
2015	sativus)		64	n/a	n/a
	Grass pea (<i>Lathyrus</i>				
2016	sativus)		39	n/a	n/a
	Grass pea (<i>Lathyrus</i>				
2017	sativus)		34	n/a	n/a

Grass pea (Lathyrus				
2018 sativus)		10 n/a	n/a	
Grass pea (Lathyrus				
2019 sativus)		122 n/a	n/a	
Grass pea (Lathyrus				
2020 sativus)		58 n/a	n/a	
Grass pea (Lathyrus				
2021 sativus)		25 n/a	n/a	
Grass pea (Lathyrus				
2022 sativus)		13 n/a	n/a	
<hr/>				
2013 Green beans	n/a	n/a	n/a	
2014 Green beans	n/a	n/a	n/a	
2015 Green beans		7780	76	4695
2016 Green beans		8610	73	5204
2017 Green beans		7580	36	5978
2018 Green beans		8070	69	4419
2019 Green beans		7580	56	3270
2020 Green beans		8190	58	6070
2021 Green beans		9030	86	4691
2022 Green beans		7190	237	4546
2023 Green beans	n/a	n/a	n/a	
<hr/>				
2013 Einkorn		738 n/a	n/a	
2014 Einkorn		454 n/a	n/a	
2015 Einkorn		867,5 n/a	n/a	
2016 Einkorn		2693,4 n/a	n/a	
2017 Einkorn		1613,2 n/a	n/a	
2018 Einkorn		737,8 n/a	n/a	
2019 Einkorn		647,8 n/a	n/a	
2020 Einkorn		246,4 n/a	n/a	
2021 Einkorn		1041,6 n/a	n/a	
<hr/>				

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	1200 (Agri Kulti estimate for organic lentils)
n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
n/a	n/a	n/a	900 (Agri Kulti estimate)

n/a	n/a	n/a	394
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n/a	n/a	n/a	397
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3244	188	86000	491
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13617	434	87000	570
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12981	90	86000	527
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10460	88	87000	848
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9955	571	94000	678
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7670	n/a	103000	n/a
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7667	n/a	123000	858
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6781	438	181000	1102
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n/a	n/a	n/a	1332
-----	-----	-----	------

9174	18738	134065	500
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6822	12150	130041	644
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14833	10040	115472	662
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n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	5000 (Agri Kulti estimate)
-----	-----	-----	----------------------------

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
-----	-----	-----	-----

n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
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Source: Italian National Institute of Statistics, Istat - might be somewhat unreliable e.g. for lupines
 Prices report the main Italian commodity exchange (Borsa Merci Bologna) listings for organic produce, unless

Year	NUC	Production (million EUR) where available	Imports (million EUR) where available	Sales to processors or intermediaries (tonnes) where available	Sales directly to consumers (tonnes) where available	Sales within agricultural enterprises (tonnes) where available	Price/tonne (EUR)	Average price at farmers' market (EUR/KG)
2013	Lupinus Albus	6000	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2014	Lupinus Albus	4759	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2015	Lupinus Albus	4748	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2016	Lupinus Albus	4717	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	180*	n/a
2017	Lupinus Albus	4720	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2018	Lupinus Albus	900	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2019	Lupinus Albus	810	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2020	Lupinus Albus	1030	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2021	Lupinus Albus	760	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2022	Lupinus Albus	940	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	415**	n/a
2023	Lupinus Albus	1103	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	452**	n/a
<hr/>								
2013	Pisum Sativum	15557	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2014	Pisum Sativum	13901	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	N/a	n/a
2015	Pisum Sativum	16004	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	N/a	n/a
2016	Pisum Sativum	22289	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	348	n/a
2017	Pisum Sativum	28889	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	425	n/a
2018	Pisum Sativum	30923	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	440	n/a
2019	Pisum Sativum	43407	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	371,33	n/a
2020	Pisum Sativum	39350	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	385	n/a
2021	Pisum Sativum	32479	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	419	n/a
2022	Pisum Sativum	16030	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	480	n/a
2023	Pisum Sativum	9613	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	415	n/a
<hr/>								
2013	Vicia faba	79794	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2014	Vicia faba	76542	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2015	Vicia faba	81613	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2016	Vicia faba	102390	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2017	Vicia faba	96087	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2018	Vicia faba	103712	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2019	Vicia faba	121354	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2020	Vicia faba	122862	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2021	Vicia faba	105629	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2022	Vicia faba	90627	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2023	Vicia faba	88936	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
<hr/>								
2013	Cicer arietinum	12228	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	572	n/a
2014	Cicer arietinum	13319	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	517	n/a
2015	Cicer arietinum	17190	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	385	n/a
2016	Cicer arietinum	22735	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	672	n/a
2017	Cicer arietinum	34093	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	955	n/a
2018	Cicer arietinum	47438	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	733	n/a

2019	Cicer arietinum	36067	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	740	n/a
2020	Cicer arietinum	33498	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	759	n/a
2021	Cicer arietinum	31052	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	880	n/a
2022	Cicer arietinum	24989	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2023	Cicer arietinum	24036	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	830	n/a
<hr/>								
2020	Triticum dicoccur	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	397,5	n/a
2021	Triticum dicoccur	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	426,4	n/a
2022	Triticum dicoccur	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	286,7	n/a
2023	Triticum dicoccur	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	245,67	n/a
<hr/>								
2020	Triticum spelta	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	373,75	n/a
2021	Triticum spelta	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	389	n/a
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is specified (*: quotations made by the Alessandria commodity exchange; ** quotations made by a pi

ulse dealer).

Sources link for each line

Year	NUC	Production	Import (million EUR) where available	Sales to processor s or intermedi aries (tonnes) where available	Sales directly to consumer s (tonnes) where available	Sales within agricultur es (tonnes) where available
2022	Vicia faba (FAVEL)	2500-3000 kg/ha	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	Cicer arietinum					
2020	(Casal Vouga)	2890 ton/year	25,8	n/a	n/a	n/a
2019	Lens culinaris	1500-2000 kg/ha	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2022	Lupinus albus	3000 kg/ha	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2017	Phaseolus vulgaris	13 460 t (16t/ha)	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2023	Pisum sativum	4159 kg/ha	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a

Price/ton ne (EUR)	Average price at farmers' market (EUR/KG)	Source
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<u>n/a</u>	<u>n/a</u>	<u>https://www.iniav.pt/images/publicacoes/2022/Cultura_da_fava.pdf</u>
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<u>n/a</u>	<u>n/a</u>	<u>https://www.lusosem.pt/noticias/grao-de-bico-uma-cultura-alternativa-e-rent</u>
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<u>n/a</u>	<u>n/a</u>	<u>https://www.confagri.pt/leguminosas-grao-consideracoes-gerais/</u>
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<u>n/a</u>	<u>n/a</u>	<u>https://proteinaverde.pt/assets/uploads/manual-de-diretrizes.pdf</u>
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<u>n/a</u>	<u>n/a</u>	<u>https://bibliotecadigital.ipb.pt/bitstream/10198/19884/1/Roman_Matheus.pd</u>
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<u>n/a</u>	<u>n/a</u>	<u>https://revistas.rcaap.pt/uiips/article/view/32551</u>
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Source: Swedish Board of Agriculture's official statistics (statistikdatabasen)

Year	NUC	Production (t)	Production (tonnes) - Organic	Import (million EUR) where available	Sales to processors or intermediaries (tonnes) where available	Sales directly to consumers (tonnes) where available	Sales within agricultural enterprises (tonnes) where available
2013	Faba bean	61300	23400	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2014	Faba bean	61100	21200	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2015	Faba bean	99100	32600	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2016	Faba bean	103900	32100	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2017	Faba bean	109400	32500	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2018	Faba bean	34800	11600	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2019	Faba bean	60200	22900	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2020	Faba bean	58400	23000	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2021	Faba bean	48800	23400	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2022	Faba bean	87600	37600	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2023	Faba bean	48300	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2013	Peas	40800	5000	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2014	Peas	46500	3800	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2015	Peas	83100	7900	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2016	Peas	92700	8900	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2017	Peas	82200	7900	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2018	Peas	48900	6400	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2019	Peas	69300	12100	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2020	Peas	72800	10100	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2021	Peas	55900	8300	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2022	Peas	86000	11700	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2023	Peas	54900	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a

Source: Swiss Granum

Year	NUC	Production (tonnes)	Conventional production (tonnes)	Organic production (tonnes)	Imports (million EUR) where available	Sales to processors or intermediaries (tonnes) where available	Sales directly to consumers (tonnes) where available
2017	Lupins	400	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2018	Lupins	500	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2019	Lupins	600	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2020	Lupins	500	400	100	n/a	n/a	n/a
2021	Lupins	600	400	200	n/a	n/a	n/a
2022	Lupins	800	500	300	n/a	n/a	n/a
2023	Lupins	600	400	200	n/a	n/a	n/a
2024	(estimated) Lupins	700	500	200	n/a	n/a	n/a

